

Analysis of Service Quality and Satisfaction Level of Customers in Banking Sector of Thoothukudi

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Dr.R.S.Thangeswari

*Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce
Kamaraj College, Thoothukudi*

B.Sharmila, Ph.D

*Research Scholar, Reg No: 18222101012017(Commerce)
Kamaraj College, Thoothukudi-3*

Affiliated to ManonmaniamSundaranar University, Tirunelveli-12

Abstract

The major aim of the study to analysis of service quality and satisfaction level of customers to assess whether bank services provided by the institutions are satisfactory to customers especially in term of service categories. This study to discover the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in banking sectors. Here 150 customers who conduct consumer banking were interviewed with a structured questionnaire. Analysis was made by using various tools like percentage Analysis.

Keywords: Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Banks of Thoothukudi.

Introduction

The banking industry in India has undergone more changes during the post -independence period. More recently, liberalization, the opening up of the economy in the 1990s and the government's decision to privatize banks by reduction in state ownership culminated in the banking reforms based on the recommendations of the Narasimham committee. This has led the Indian banking industry to experience difficult times. In such testing times of mature and acute competitive pressures, it is very urgent and important that banks are able to retain a loyal base of clients. To attain this and to improve their market and profit positions, banks in India have to formulate their strategies and policies towards increasing customer satisfaction levels. Banking institutions across the globe have recognized the importance of customer satisfaction and of developing and maintaining enduring relationship with their customers as two crucial parameters leading to increased business profits.

Review Literature

Aravmudhan. V (2014), analysed the relationship among service quality, customer satisfaction and customer retention in Lakshmi Vilas Bank at Tiruchengode town. It addresses whether the dimensions

of service quality impacts customer satisfaction which eventually leading to customer retention. Correlation was used to analyse the relationship among service quality, customer satisfaction and customer retention. Service quality and customer satisfaction have a positive correlation with customer retention. Hence, the bank provides quality services and also highly satisfies and retains their customers. Further, the bank implements and create awareness on e-corner facilities to satisfy and retain their customers. It reduces the employees' burden and help to maintain a long term relationship between the employees and the customers because employees are the face of the bank.

Abdul A R. (2014) evaluated the customers' satisfaction towards the banking services rendered by the SBI in Kanyakumari District. The author conducted a literature search on banking services of SBI interviewing of its 150 customers and thoroughly scrutinized how it caters to the banking needs of the inhabitants of Kanyakumari district. The study also focused on various factors that determine the customers' satisfaction like employees' behaviour, banking services, banking performance, infra- structure facility, loan oriented services and other value added services. Analysis was made by using various tools like percentage Analysis, Chi- Square Test and charts. The result showed that there is a significant relationship between the variable of customer satisfaction and banking services of the SBI and the customers have a medium level of satisfaction. The SBI could consider the researcher's suggestions in order to alleviate its reputation and customer satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the various services provided by the banking sector in Thoothukudi district
- To study the level of customer satisfaction towards the services provided by the banking sector in Thoothukudi District.
- To make suggestions for improving the bank's customer services.

Method of data Collection

The study is based on both primary data and secondary data. Primary source of data were collected from customers through structured interview schedule by way of personal interview. Secondary data were collected from books, journals and Websites.

Sampling Techniques and Size

Convenient sampling method is used. The researcher has taken 150 samples from customers of banks in Thoothukudi district.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The required data has been collected by way of a questionnaire and it has been analysis and interpreted with the help of tables with relevant descriptions.

Table 1 Gender of the respondents

S.No	Gender	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Male	95	63
2	Female	55	37
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

It is inferred that the above table among 150 sample respondents, 63 percentages belong to male group and 37 percentages belong to female group. Hence it is understood that male members are more than female members.

Table 2 Age Wise Classification by the Respondents

S.No	Age	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	20-30	21	14
2	30-40	78	52
3	40-50	36	24
4	Above 50	15	10
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table reveals that thirty 14% respondents fall under the age group of 20 to 30years, 52% respondents fall under the age group of 30 to 40 years, 24% respondents fall under the age group 40 to 50 years, 15% respondents fall under the age group Above 50. The majority of the respondent falls under the age group of 30 to 40 years.

Table 3 Participants Educational Background

S.No	Education Level	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Higher Secondary	12	8
2	Diploma	22	15
3	Graduate	86	57
4	Post Graduate	30	20
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that out of 150 total respondents, 57% are graduates, 20% are post graduate, 15% are diploma and 8% of them are higher secondary. From this survey the researcher found that 57% of the respondents are graduates.

Table 4 Participants Occupation Background

S.No	Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Business	23	15
2	Government employee	55	37
3	Private employee	65	43
4	Others	7	5
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 15% of the respondents are businessman, 37% of them are government employees, 43% of private employee and 5% of respondents are others. The majority of the respondent falls under the private employees.

Table 5 On the basis of Type of Account

S.No	Type of Account	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Saving account	90	60
2	Fixed deposit account	27	18
3	Current account	25	17
4	Others	8	5
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table indicates 60% of the respondents are saving account, 18% of them have fixed deposit, 17% of the respondents are current account and 8% of the respondents are others. The majority of the respondent falls under the saving account.

Table 6 No of user in Banking Sectors

S.No	Banking sectors	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	ICICI	17	12
2	AXIS	11	7
3	TMBL	23	15
4	HDFC	6	4
5	SBI	36	24
6	Indian Bank	18	12
7	IOB	26	17
8	Canara Bank	13	9
Total		150	100

Source: Primary data

The above table indicates 12% of the respondents are using ICICI, 7% of the respondents are using AXIS. 15% of the respondents are using TMBL, 4% of the respondents are using HDFC, 24% of the respondents are using SBI, 12% of the respondents are using IB, 17% of the respondents are using IOB, and 9% of the respondents are using Canara Bank.

Table 7 The Gender of the Respondents and their Level of Satisfaction

Null hypothesis (H0)

There is no significant between the gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction with regard to analysis of service quality and satisfaction level of customers in banking sector of thoothukudi.

Total	Level of satisfaction			Gender
	Low	Medium	High	
Male	31	46	18	95
Female	15	32	8	55
Total	46	78	26	150

Source: Primary data

Chi-Square Tests			
Particulars	Value	Df	Sig.value
Chi-Square	12.2	8	15.57*

Findings

- Majority of the respondents are male
- Majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 36 to 45 years.
- Majority of the respondents are graduates
- Majority of the respondents are private Employee.
- Majority of the respondents are saving a/c holders
- Majority of the respondents are using SBI bank.

- There is no significant between the gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction with regard to analysis of service quality and satisfaction level of customers in banking sector of Thoothukudi.

Suggestions

The management needs to improve quality services so as to satisfy customer's needs. The bank needs to pay much attention on the customer complaints in order satisfy the customer's expectation. In order to retain the existing customers and to improve service quality, the bank should continuously maintain error-free transactions, since bank accounts and figures are very sensitive for each and every customer.

Conclusion

The banks should give more special attention to 'the customer's by giving timely training to the employees to conduct themselves better services and as well as quality of services. Perhaps this would definitely lead to a flourishing economy, since customer satisfaction is the pivot of a successful banking infrastructure.

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